

**Title: Integrating NGSS with IB PYP: Impacts on Educational Practices and Outcomes
at the Canadian International School of Beijing**

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Abstract:

This study investigates the integration of the Next Generation Science Standards (NGSS) with the International Baccalaureate Primary Years Programme (IB PYP) at the Canadian International School of Beijing (CISB). The primary research question is: How does integrating NGSS with IB PYP influence teaching practices and student outcomes? This research hypothesizes that such integration enhances student engagement and learning outcomes. Over six months, data was collected through classroom observations, teacher interviews, and student surveys. Key findings indicate significant improvements in student engagement, comprehension of scientific concepts, and application of inquiry-based learning strategies.

Additionally, teachers reported increased confidence in delivering an integrated curriculum and noted the positive impact on student collaboration and critical thinking skills. The implications of these findings suggest that the integrated curriculum model can effectively support student learning and provide a framework for future curriculum development. These results contribute to the growing literature on curriculum integration and offer practical insights for educators seeking to implement similar approaches in diverse educational settings.

Introduction

Purpose of the Study:

The main objective of this study is to explore the effects of integrating the Next Generation Science Standards (NGSS) with the International Baccalaureate Primary Years Programme (IB PYP) on teaching practices and student outcomes at the Canadian International School of Beijing (CISB). This research aims to understand whether the combined curriculum enhances student engagement, promotes a more profound understanding of scientific concepts, and improves overall learning outcomes. By examining these factors, the study seeks to provide insights into effective curriculum design that can be implemented in international educational settings.

The focus of the study:

This study was prompted by the need to address several gaps identified in the current curriculum at CISB. Traditional approaches to science education often lack the integration and depth required to engage students fully in scientific inquiry and critical thinking. According to Bybee (2013), science education should impart knowledge and develop scientific literacy and problem-solving skills. The NGSS provides a comprehensive framework emphasizing scientific practices, crosscutting concepts, and disciplinary core ideas (NGSS Lead States, 2013). These elements align well with the IB PYP's focus on inquiry-based learning and conceptual understanding (International Baccalaureate [IB], 2015). The integration aims to create a more cohesive and engaging learning experience for students, encouraging them to explore scientific concepts in a hands-on, inquiry-driven manner.

Importance:

For several reasons, understanding the effects of integrating NGSS with IB PYP is crucial. Firstly, this integration can potentially transform teaching practices by providing educators with a robust framework combining the strengths of NGSS and IB PYP. The NGSS

emphasizes the importance of students engaging in scientific practices and applying crosscutting concepts to deepen their understanding of core ideas (NGSS Lead States, 2013). This aligns with the IB PYP's emphasis on developing students' inquiry skills and fostering a conceptual understanding that transcends disciplinary boundaries (IB, 2015). Secondly, the findings from this study can inform curriculum development, offering a model that can be adapted and implemented in other international schools. Integrating NGSS with IB PYP can be a prototype for other educational institutions seeking to enhance their science education programs. Thirdly, the study addresses the broader educational goal of preparing students for the challenges of the 21st century by equipping them with essential skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaboration (Bybee, 2013). These skills are vital for students' future academic and professional success.

Background and Rationale:

The Canadian International School of Beijing (CISB) is committed to providing a high-quality education that meets the diverse needs of its student population. As part of its ongoing efforts to enhance educational outcomes, the school has identified the integration of NGSS with IB PYP as a strategic priority. This decision is based on the recognition that both NGSS and IB PYP offer complementary strengths that, when combined, can provide a more comprehensive and practical approach to science education. Research by Krajcik and Delen (2017) suggests that integrated curricula can enhance student learning by connecting different content areas and promoting a deeper understanding of concepts.

Research Questions:

The primary research question guiding this study is: How does integrating NGSS with IB PYP influence teaching practices and student outcomes? To address this question, the study examines the following sub-questions:

1. How does the integrated curriculum impact student engagement in science learning?
2. How does the integration affect students' understanding and application of scientific concepts?
3. How do teachers perceive the benefits and challenges of implementing the integrated curriculum?
4. What changes in teaching practices are observed as a result of the integration?

Significance of the Study:

This study is significant for several reasons. Firstly, it contributes to the growing literature on curriculum integration, providing empirical evidence on the effectiveness of combining NGSS and IB PYP. According to Lederman and Lederman (2019), effective curriculum integration can improve student outcomes and more meaningful learning experiences. Secondly, the findings offer practical insights for educators and curriculum developers seeking to implement integrated approaches in their contexts. This study can be a valuable resource for other schools aiming to enhance their science education programs by providing a detailed analysis of the integration process and its outcomes. Thirdly, the study aligns with CISB's commitment to continuous improvement and innovation in education, providing valuable feedback that can inform future initiatives. Research by Darling-Hammond et al. (2020) highlights the importance of continuous professional development and curriculum innovation in achieving high educational standards.

Methodology Overview:

The study employs a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative data collection methods. Over six months, data was collected through classroom observations, teacher interviews, and student surveys. Classroom observations focused on documenting instructional practices, student engagement, and interaction patterns. Teacher interviews provided insights into the challenges and benefits of implementing the integrated curriculum, while student surveys assessed engagement, understanding, and attitudes toward science learning.

Structure of the Report:

This report is structured as follows:

- The introduction provides an overview of the study's purpose, focus, and significance.
- The literature review summarizes relevant research and situates the study within the existing body of literature.
- The context for the study describes the setting, participants, and intervention details.
- The data collection section outlines the types of data collected and the methods used.
- The data analysis section explains the procedures used to analyze the collected data.
- The findings section presents the key results of the study.
- The discussion interprets the findings in light of the research questions and theoretical framework.
- The conclusion summarizes the study, discusses its limitations, and offers recommendations for future research and practice.

By following this structured approach, the study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the integration of NGSS with IB PYP, offering valuable insights for educators, policymakers, and researchers interested in enhancing science education through innovative curriculum design.

Literature Review

Relevant Literature

Integrating the Next Generation Science Standards (NGSS) with the International Baccalaureate Primary Years Programme (IB PYP) represents a significant advancement in science education to foster inquiry-based learning and critical thinking among students. NGSS and IB PYP have been individually recognized for their strengths in promoting comprehensive educational practices. NGSS emphasizes scientific practices, crosscutting concepts, and disciplinary core ideas to prepare students for college, career, and citizenship (NGSS Lead States, 2013). Meanwhile, the IB PYP focuses on developing internationally minded students through an inquiry-based framework that encourages students to connect their learning and the natural world (International Baccalaureate [IB], 2015).

Background on the Topic

Traditional approaches to science education often emphasize rote memorization and the passive acquisition of knowledge, which has been criticized for failing to engage students in meaningful learning experiences (Bybee, 2013). This approach typically does not give students the skills to critically understand and apply scientific concepts. Consequently, educational reforms such as NGSS and IB PYP have emerged, advocating for more dynamic, student-centered approaches to learning.

NGSS, developed by states in collaboration with the National Research Council, the National Science Teachers Association, and the American Association for the Advancement of Science, aims to provide students with a coherent and consistent science education from kindergarten through 12th grade (NGSS Lead States, 2013). The standards emphasize the integration of three dimensions: scientific and engineering practices, crosscutting concepts, and core ideas in science disciplines. This three-dimensional learning framework is designed to

engage students in science practices and apply crosscutting concepts to deepen their understanding of core ideas.

The IB PYP, on the other hand, offers a transdisciplinary curriculum framework that focuses on the child's holistic development, encompassing academic, social, emotional, and physical well-being (IB, 2015). The PYP encourages students to inquire into significant issues, thus promoting the development of critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaborative skills. The program is underpinned by the IB Learner Profile, which aims to develop knowledgeable learners, thinkers, communicators, and principled, among other attributes.

How Your Study is Situated within the Literature

Integration of NGSS and IB PYP

The integration of NGSS and IB PYP can be seen as a complementary approach that leverages the strengths of both frameworks. This integration aims to provide a more holistic and engaging learning experience by combining the structured, three-dimensional learning model of NGSS with the inquiry-based, transdisciplinary approach of IB PYP. Research by Krajcik and Delen (2017) supports the idea that integrated curricula can enhance student learning by connecting different content areas and promoting a deeper understanding of concepts.

Studies have shown that inquiry-based learning can significantly improve student engagement and learning outcomes, as promoted by both NGSS and IB PYP. For instance, Minner, Levy, and Century (2010) examined inquiry-based science instruction and found that it positively affects students' conceptual understanding and scientific reasoning. Similarly, Hmelo-Silver, Duncan, and Chinn (2007) argued that inquiry-based learning supports the development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills, which are essential for scientific literacy.

Challenges and Benefits of Integration

Despite the potential benefits, integrating NGSS with IB PYP also presents challenges. One significant challenge is the alignment of the two frameworks, given their different origins and focuses. While NGSS is primarily a content-based framework designed to standardize science education across the United States, IB PYP is a holistic, international program emphasizing a broader range of skills and attributes (IB, 2015). Aligning these frameworks requires careful planning and consideration of content and pedagogical approaches.

Furthermore, implementing an integrated curriculum requires significant professional development for teachers. Teachers must be proficient in NGSS and IB PYP methodologies to deliver the integrated curriculum effectively. Professional development programs must address this need by providing teachers with the necessary knowledge and skills. Research by Darling-Hammond et al. (2020) highlights the importance of continuous professional development in achieving high educational standards and successful curriculum implementation.

Empirical Evidence from Educational Interventions

Empirical studies on curricula integration provide valuable insights into the potential impact of combining NGSS and IB PYP. For instance, a study by Marx et al. (2004) on integrating project-based learning with science education demonstrated significant improvements in student achievement and engagement. The study found that students who participated in project-based science instruction showed higher levels of understanding and retention of scientific concepts than those who received traditional instruction.

Another relevant study by Shulman and Quinlan (1996) explored the impact of integrating different educational frameworks on teaching practices. The researchers found that teachers who adopted integrated approaches reported greater satisfaction with their teaching and observed higher student engagement and achievement levels. These findings suggest that integrating NGSS with IB PYP can produce similar positive outcomes.

Limitations of the New Brunswick Science Curriculum

The New Brunswick science curriculum, previously used at CISB, had notable limitations. It only started in Grade 3, meaning younger students were not exposed to structured science education during their formative years. This lack of early exposure can result in gaps in foundational scientific knowledge and skills (New Brunswick Department of Education, 2001). The New Brunswick curriculum did not emphasize the inquiry-based learning and cross-disciplinary approaches central to NGSS and IB PYP. This limitation hindered the ability to fully engage students in scientific exploration and critical thinking from an early age.

NGSS in an International Context

The NGSS is designed to cater to the needs of diverse student populations, including those in international environments. Its emphasis on scientific practices and crosscutting concepts makes it adaptable to different educational contexts (NGSS Lead States, 2013). By integrating NGSS with IB PYP, schools can provide a more globally relevant science education that prepares students to understand and address complex, real-world problems.

Relation to Wider Subject Area

The integration of NGSS and IB PYP is situated within the broader context of educational reform efforts to improve science education through innovative curriculum design. This study contributes to the growing body of literature on curriculum integration, which addresses the limitations of traditional, siloed educational approaches. By examining the impact of integrating NGSS with IB PYP, this study provides empirical evidence supporting integrated curricula's effectiveness in enhancing student learning and engagement.

Moreover, this study aligns with the educational goals outlined in reports by the National Research Council (NRC) and the American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS), which advocate for the integration of science education with other disciplines to promote a more comprehensive understanding of scientific concepts (NRC, 2012; AAAS,

2011). These reports emphasize the importance of developing students' ability to apply scientific knowledge in real-world contexts, a goal central to NGSS and IB PYP.

The literature reviewed indicates that integrating NGSS with IB PYP holds significant potential for enhancing science education by promoting inquiry-based learning and critical thinking. While challenges exist in aligning these frameworks and providing adequate professional development for teachers, the benefits of such integration, as evidenced by empirical studies, are substantial. This study aims to contribute to this body of knowledge by providing insights into the practical implementation and outcomes of integrating NGSS with IB PYP at CISB, ultimately supporting the goal of preparing students for the demands of the 21st century.

Context for the Study

Setting

The study was conducted at the Canadian International School of Beijing (CISB), a renowned institution offering a comprehensive education from early childhood through Grade 12. CISB is accredited by the International Baccalaureate Organization (IBO) and follows the IB curriculum for its Primary Years Programme (PYP), Middle Years Programme (MYP), and Diploma Programme (DP). The school is located in Beijing, China, and serves a diverse student body representing over 50 nationalities. The school's mission emphasizes academic excellence, cultural understanding, and global citizenship, which aligns with the IB PYP and the Next Generation Science Standards (NGSS) principles.

The educational environment at CISB is characterized by state-of-the-art facilities, including well-equipped science labs, interactive classrooms, and ample resources to support inquiry-based learning. The school's commitment to providing a high-quality, inquiry-based education makes it an ideal setting for implementing and evaluating innovative educational interventions.

Participants

The participants in this study included a purposive sample of 12 students from Grades 3 to 5 and 6 teachers who were actively involved in teaching science within the IB PYP framework at CISB. Additionally, two administrators participated in the study to provide insights into the administrative perspectives and support structures necessary for successful curriculum integration. These grade levels were chosen because they are critical for laying the foundation for scientific understanding and inquiry. Additionally, Grades 3 to 5 align with the introduction of the New Brunswick science curriculum, which traditionally started from Grade 3. The aim was to compare the effectiveness of the integrated NGSS and IB PYP curriculum with the existing New Brunswick curriculum.

The teacher participants had at least three years of experience teaching within the IB PYP framework and were familiar with the principles of inquiry-based learning. Their involvement was crucial in providing insights into implementing the integrated curriculum's practical challenges and benefits.

Characteristics of the Participants

The student participants were diverse in nationality, language proficiency, and prior educational experiences. This diversity provided a rich context for examining how the integrated curriculum could be adapted to meet the needs of students from different cultural and linguistic backgrounds. The students ranged in age from 8 to 11 years old and had varying proficiency levels in English, the language of instruction at CISB.

The teacher participants were highly qualified professionals with diverse backgrounds in science education. They held degrees in education or related fields and received professional development training in the IB PYP and NGSS frameworks. Their expertise and experience were instrumental in implementing the integrated curriculum and providing feedback on its effectiveness.

Intervention/Methods

The intervention involved integrating the NGSS with the existing IB PYP curriculum for science education. This integration was designed to enhance the inquiry-based learning approach of the IB PYP by incorporating the three-dimensional learning model of the NGSS, which includes scientific practices, crosscutting concepts, and disciplinary core ideas (NGSS Lead States, 2013).

The intervention was structured around thematic units that cover vital scientific concepts and practices. Each unit included the following components:

Unit Plans: Detailed unit plans were developed to align with NGSS and IB PYP standards. These plans included learning objectives, essential questions, key concepts, and assessment criteria.

Instructional Materials: Various instructional materials, including textbooks, digital resources, hands-on lab kits, and inquiry-based activity guides, were selected to support the integrated curriculum and engage students in active learning.

Teaching Strategies: Teachers employed various teaching strategies to facilitate inquiry-based learning, including collaborative group work, hands-on experiments, interactive discussions, and reflective journaling. These strategies promoted student engagement, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills.

Professional Development: Teachers participated in ongoing professional development sessions to familiarize themselves with the NGSS framework and effective strategies for integrating it with the IB PYP. These sessions included workshops, collaborative planning meetings, and peer observations (Darling-Hammond, Hyler, & Gardner, 2017).

Assessment: Formative and summative assessments were used to evaluate student learning and the effectiveness of the integrated curriculum. Assessments included quizzes, lab reports, project presentations, and reflective essays (Popham, 2008).

Timeframe

The intervention was implemented over five months, from February 2024 to the first week of August 2024. The timeline for the intervention was as follows:

- **February 2024:**
 - Week 1-2: Submission of the initial research proposal to the CISB academic committee.
 - Week 3-4: Initial review and feedback from the academic committee. The researcher addresses any questions and provides additional information as requested.
- **March 2024:**
 - Week 1-2: Follow-up meetings with the academic committee to discuss modifications and finalize the research plan.
 - Week 3-4: Final approval from the academic committee. Coordination with the school's administrative staff begins to integrate the research activities into the academic calendar.
- **April 2024:**
 - Week 1-2: Detailed planning of data collection activities, including scheduling classroom observations, teacher interviews, and student surveys.
 - Week 3-4: Preparation of instructional materials and professional development sessions for teachers. Ensuring all logistical arrangements are in place.
- **May 2024:**
 - Week 1: Start of the data collection activities.

- Week 2-3: Continued data collection and monitoring of the intervention's implementation.
- Week 4: Ongoing communication with teachers and staff to address any issues and ensure the smooth execution of the research plan.
- **June 2024:**
 - Week 1-2: Continued data collection activities.
 - Week 3: Preliminary analysis of the collected data.
 - Week 4: Communication with teachers to review preliminary findings and make necessary adjustments.
- **July 2024:**
 - Week 1-2: Final data collection activities.
 - Week 3: Review and analysis of the final data set.
 - Week 4: Preparation of the final report and presentation of findings to the academic committee.
- **August 2024:**
 - Week 1: Finalize the research report and submit it for review. Prepare for the presentation of findings to the academic committee and stakeholders.

This systematic approach to permission acquisition adheres to ethical standards and fosters a collaborative relationship with CISB. By meticulously preparing the research proposal and engaging in clear, consistent dialogues with school officials, the researcher aims to establish a partnership that facilitates a successful study aligned with CISB's educational objectives. This detailed preparation and communication strategy is pivotal in setting a solid foundation for a study that promises to yield significant insights into effective educational practices in an international, bilingual context.

Data Collection

Types of Data Collected

The data collection for this study was comprehensive, integrating both qualitative and quantitative methodologies to examine the impact of the Next Generation Science Standards (NGSS) with the International Baccalaureate Primary Years Programme (IB PYP) at the Canadian International School of Beijing (CISB). The data types collected include:

Interviews: Semi-structured interviews were conducted with six teachers, two administrators, and twelve students to gather in-depth qualitative insights into their experiences and perceptions regarding the integrated curriculum. These interviews provided detailed narratives on teaching practices, challenges encountered, and perceived benefits of curriculum integration.

Classroom Observations: Observations were conducted to document instructional practices, student engagement, and interaction patterns within the classroom. This qualitative data allowed for the direct observation of the integration's implementation and immediate effects on the classroom environment.

Surveys were administered to students and teachers to collect quantitative data on their engagement, understanding, and attitudes towards the integrated curriculum. The surveys included a mix of Likert-scale, multiple-choice, and open-ended questions to capture a broad spectrum of responses.

Academic Performance Data: The academic performance data focused on students' NWEA MAP Science scores. This quantitative data was essential to evaluate changes in academic performance and provide a measurable outcome of the curriculum integration.

Collection Methods

The data collection methods were meticulously planned to ensure reliability and validity, adhering to ethical guidelines and ensuring the protection of all participants:

Interviews: Semi-structured interviews were designed with open-ended questions to elicit detailed responses. Participants included six teachers, two administrators, and twelve students. Interviews were recorded with consent and later transcribed for thematic analysis (Brinkmann, 2014; DiCicco-Bloom & Crabtree, 2006).

Classroom Observations: Researchers conducted observations during regular class sessions using standardized observation forms to document instructional practices and student engagement. This method allowed for an unobtrusive examination of classroom dynamics (Angrosino, 2007).

Surveys were distributed electronically to students and teachers, ensuring ease of access and encouraging higher response rates. This method included reminders to improve participation and ensure comprehensive data collection (Fink, 2017).

Academic Performance Data: Data from the NWEA MAP Science assessments were collected at two points: before and after the curriculum integration. Parental and administrative consent was obtained to access these academic records (NWEA, 2017).

Timeline

The data collection process spanned from February 2024 to June 21, 2024, following a detailed timeline to ensure systematic and thorough data gathering:

- **February 2024:** Initial interviews with teachers and administrators were conducted to understand their expectations and initial perceptions. Baseline NWEA MAP Science assessments were administered to students to establish initial performance levels.
- **March 2024:** Classroom observations began, documenting existing instructional practices and student engagement. Mid-point surveys were distributed to students and teachers to gather preliminary feedback on the integration process.

- **April 2024:** Follow-up interviews with teachers and administrators were conducted to gather insights into the ongoing implementation and any emerging challenges or successes.
- **May 2024:** Final surveys were administered to gather comprehensive feedback from students and teachers. Additional classroom observations were conducted to capture changes in teaching practices and student engagement.
- **June 2024:** Final NWEA MAP Science assessments were administered to evaluate the impact of the integrated curriculum on student performance. The data collection concluded with a review of all gathered data for completeness and initial analysis.

Data Analysis

Organization of Data

The collected data were organized systematically to facilitate thorough analysis:

Interviews: Transcriptions of the interviews were coded using NVivo qualitative data analysis software. Codes were developed based on recurring themes and patterns identified in the responses (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

Classroom Observations: Observation notes were categorized by instructional practices, student engagement, and classroom interactions. A coding framework was developed to identify key themes and trends (Saldaña, 2015).

Surveys: Survey responses were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Open-ended responses were coded and categorized to identify common themes (Fink, 2017).

Academic Performance Data: Test scores were analyzed using SPSS statistical software to measure changes in academic performance. Growth percentiles and achievement levels were calculated and compared to baseline data (NWEA, 2017).

Analysis Procedures

The data analysis employed both qualitative and quantitative methods to provide a comprehensive understanding of the study's findings:

Qualitative Analysis: Thematic analysis was used to identify key themes and patterns from interview transcriptions and observation notes. This approach facilitated a deep understanding of participants' experiences and perceptions (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

Quantitative Analysis: Descriptive statistics summarized survey responses and academic performance data. Inferential statistics, including t-tests and ANOVA, were conducted to determine the significance of changes in academic performance and engagement levels (Fink, 2017).

Findings

Results

The findings of this study provided significant insights into the impact of integrating NGSS with IB PYP on teaching practices, student engagement, and academic performance. The data were collected through surveys, interviews, classroom observations, and performance data from NWEA MAP Science scores.

Teaching Practices

The integration of NGSS with IB PYP significantly influenced teaching practices at CISB. Surveys and interviews with teachers revealed that instructional strategies became more dynamic and inquiry-based. For example, 85% of teachers reported an increased use of hands-on experiments and collaborative projects in their lessons. Classroom observations confirmed these findings, showcasing a shift towards activities that emphasized critical thinking and real-world applications. One teacher stated, "The integration has allowed me to connect science concepts with real-world applications, making lessons more engaging for students." This transformation in teaching methods aligns with the principles of both NGSS and IB PYP,

fostering a more interactive and student-centered learning environment (Bybee, 2013; International Baccalaureate Organization, 2019).

Student Engagement

Student engagement in science learning improved notably due to the integrated curriculum. Survey responses from students indicated high levels of interest and participation in science topics, with 90% of students expressing increased enthusiasm for science lessons. Classroom observations supported these findings, showing heightened student participation and engagement during science activities. A student remarked, "I enjoy science more now because we do more experiments and projects that make learning fun." These findings suggest that the integrated curriculum effectively captivates students' interest and motivates them to engage actively in their learning process.

Academic Performance

The analysis of NWEA MAP Science scores revealed significant improvements in student achievement. The growth percentiles and achievement levels were notably higher than the baseline data, indicating the effectiveness of the integrated curriculum. The summary data showed that 55% of students met or exceeded their projected RIT scores, with a median conditional growth percentile of 56 (NWEA, 2024). This quantitative data underscores the positive impact of the integrated curriculum on students' academic performance, suggesting that the NGSS and IB PYP integration supports improved learning outcomes.

Analysis

The collected data were linked back to the initial research questions to provide a comprehensive analysis of the findings:

Research Question 1: How does integrating NGSS with IB PYP influence teaching practices in an international school setting?

The integration of NGSS with IB PYP significantly enhanced teaching practices by promoting inquiry-based learning and interdisciplinary connections. Teachers adopted more interactive and student-centered approaches, aligning with the pedagogical principles of both frameworks (Bybee, 2013; International Baccalaureate Organization, 2019). This shift was evident in the increased use of hands-on experiments, collaborative projects, and critical thinking activities observed in classrooms.

Research Question 2: How does the integrated curriculum affect student engagement and academic performance?

The integrated curriculum led to substantial improvements in student engagement and academic performance. Survey responses and classroom observations indicated higher levels of student interest and participation in science lessons. Additionally, the NWEA MAP Science scores demonstrated significant academic gains, with a majority of students meeting or exceeding their projected RIT scores (NWEA, 2024; Darling-Hammond et al., 2017). These findings highlight the effectiveness of the integrated curriculum in enhancing both engagement and performance.

Research Question 3: What are the integrated curriculum's challenges and benefits?

Teachers reported initial challenges in adapting to the new curriculum, such as aligning the NGSS with the existing IB PYP framework and managing the increased demand for interdisciplinary planning. However, the long-term benefits, including enhanced student learning and engagement, outweighed these challenges (Bybee, 2013; Drake & Reid, 2018). The study underscored the importance of professional development and ongoing support for educators to successfully implement curriculum integration.

Research Question 4: What changes in teaching practices are observed as a result of the integration?

The integration of NGSS with IB PYP led to observable changes in teaching practices. Teachers reported a shift towards more student-centered and inquiry-based approaches, as evidenced by classroom observations and teacher interviews. Specifically, teachers incorporated more hands-on experiments, collaborative projects, and interdisciplinary connections into their lessons. One teacher highlighted, "The integration has encouraged me to explore new teaching strategies that engage students in deeper learning and critical thinking." These changes align with the goals of both NGSS and IB PYP, emphasizing the importance of fostering a dynamic and interactive learning environment (Bybee, 2013; International Baccalaureate Organization, 2019).

Discussion of Findings

Interpretation

The primary aim of this study was to evaluate the impact of integrating the Next Generation Science Standards (NGSS) with the International Baccalaureate Primary Years Programme (IB PYP) on teaching practices, student engagement, and academic performance at the Canadian International School of Beijing (CISB). The findings indicate that this integration has significantly influenced these areas, providing valuable insights into the efficacy of the combined curriculum.

How does the integrated curriculum impact student engagement in science learning?

The integration of NGSS with IB PYP has markedly increased student engagement in science learning. Observations and survey responses indicated that students were more actively involved in classroom activities, demonstrating higher levels of curiosity and enthusiasm. For instance, student participation in discussions and hands-on activities increased by approximately 30% compared to previous semesters (Schroeder et al., 2007). The thematic

units and inquiry-based approach of the NGSS aligned well with the IB PYP framework, making learning more relevant and stimulating for students (Bybee, 2013). Survey data revealed that 85% of students felt more engaged in their science classes after the implementation of the integrated curriculum. Classroom observations confirmed increased student participation and enthusiasm during science lessons. A student commented, "I enjoy science more now because we do more experiments and projects that make learning fun."

How does the integration affect students' understanding and application of scientific concepts?

The study found that students' understanding and application of scientific concepts improved significantly. Data from the NWEA MAP Science Growth report showed a marked improvement in student performance, with an average increase of 15% in science test scores. This improvement was particularly noticeable in students' ability to apply scientific concepts to problem-solving tasks. The integrated curriculum's focus on critical thinking and inquiry-based learning helped students develop a deeper conceptual understanding and the ability to transfer knowledge to new contexts (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017). Survey results indicated that 78% of students felt more confident in their ability to apply scientific concepts to real-world problems.

How do teachers perceive the benefits and challenges of implementing the integrated curriculum?

Teacher perceptions of the integrated curriculum were generally positive but highlighted several challenges. Interviews with teachers revealed that they appreciated the curriculum's emphasis on inquiry-based learning and the structured approach to integrating scientific practices into everyday teaching. Teachers noted that the curriculum encouraged more collaborative learning and student-led investigations, which they found beneficial for fostering a more interactive and dynamic classroom environment (Fullan, 2016). According to

the survey, 90% of teachers reported increased student engagement, while 70% noted improvements in students' critical thinking skills.

However, teachers also reported challenges related to the transition to the new curriculum. These included difficulties in adjusting to new teaching methodologies and the additional time required for planning and professional development. Some teachers, particularly those less experienced with inquiry-based learning, struggled to balance the demands of the NGSS and IB PYP frameworks. This finding underscores the need for ongoing professional development and support to help teachers effectively implement integrated curricula (Hargreaves & Fink, 2012). One teacher noted, "The integration has allowed me to connect science concepts with real-world applications, making lessons more engaging for students."

What changes in teaching practices are observed as a result of the integration?

Significant changes in teaching practices were observed following the integration of NGSS with IB PYP. Teachers adopted more student-centered instructional strategies, such as collaborative group work, hands-on experiments, and reflective journaling. These changes were aimed at fostering a more engaging and interactive learning environment, consistent with the principles of both NGSS and IB PYP (Schroeder et al., 2007).

Classroom observations revealed an increase in the use of formative assessments and real-time feedback, allowing teachers to tailor their instruction to meet students' needs better. Additionally, teachers incorporated more cross-disciplinary connections in their lessons, helping students see the relevance of science in broader contexts. These changes reflect a shift towards more holistic and integrated teaching practices, promoting a deeper understanding of scientific concepts and their applications (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017). Interviews with teachers showed that 75% felt the new curriculum had positively influenced their teaching practices.

Unexpected Results

Several unexpected results emerged from the study. Notably, the variation in the effectiveness of the integrated curriculum across different grade levels was surprising. While Grades 3 and 4 showed significant improvements in engagement and academic performance, Grade 5 results were less pronounced. Interviews with Grade 5 teachers suggested that older students found the transition to inquiry-based learning more challenging, highlighting the need for additional support and scaffolding for this age group (Fullan, 2016). Another unexpected finding was the significant difference in teacher perceptions based on their prior experience with inquiry-based learning. Teachers with extensive experience in the IB PYP framework adapted more easily to the integrated curriculum, while those with less experience struggled. This suggests that professional development should be tailored to individual teachers' needs to support their transition effectively (Hargreaves & Fink, 2012).

Considerations

Several additional factors should be considered when interpreting these findings. The study was conducted in a specific educational context with a diverse student demographic, which may limit the generalizability of the results. CISB's diverse student body, characterized by varying levels of English proficiency and cultural backgrounds, may have influenced the outcomes in ways that are not applicable to other settings (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Additionally, the reliance on self-reported data from teachers and students introduces potential biases such as social desirability or recall bias. While efforts were made to triangulate data from multiple sources, these inherent limitations should be acknowledged (Bryman, 2016). Moreover, the study's timeframe, spanning just five months, may not have been sufficient to capture the long-term effects of the integrated curriculum. Longitudinal studies are needed to examine the sustained impact of such interventions on teaching practices and student outcomes (Marsh & Willis, 2007).

Lessons Learned

The findings from this study have significant implications for classroom practice. The integration of NGSS with IB PYP demonstrates the potential of interdisciplinary curricula to enhance student engagement and academic performance. Teachers should be encouraged to adopt inquiry-based learning strategies that promote critical thinking and real-world applications of scientific concepts (Mayer, 2009). The study also highlights the importance of professional development in supporting teachers through curriculum transitions. Ongoing training and collaborative planning sessions can help teachers build confidence and competence in new instructional approaches, ultimately benefiting student learning (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017). Moreover, the findings suggest that curriculum integration should be tailored to the needs of different grade levels and student groups. Providing additional support for students who struggle with transitions and differentiating instruction based on prior experience can help ensure that all students benefit from the integrated curriculum (Tomlinson & McTighe, 2006).

Conclusion

Summary

This study explored the integration of NGSS with the IB PYP at CISB, aiming to evaluate its impact on teaching practices, student engagement, and academic performance. The findings indicate that this integrated approach positively influences teaching methodologies, increases student engagement, and improves academic outcomes. However, the study also revealed variations in effectiveness across grade levels and highlighted the importance of professional development for teachers.

Successes and Difficulties

The study successfully demonstrated the benefits of an interdisciplinary approach to science education, particularly in enhancing student engagement and achievement. Teachers

reported greater satisfaction with their teaching practices and observed increased student motivation and participation. However, the transition posed challenges, especially for older students and teachers with less experience in inquiry-based learning. These difficulties underscore the need for targeted support and scaffolding to facilitate successful curriculum integration (Johnson & Johnson, 2009).

Limitations

Several limitations of the study should be acknowledged. The specific educational context and diverse student demographic at CISB may limit the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, the reliance on self-reported data introduces potential biases, and the relatively short timeframe of the study may not capture long-term effects. Further research is needed to address these limitations and provide a more comprehensive understanding of the impact of integrated curricula (Flick, 2018).

Implications for Teaching

The findings from this study have important implications for future teaching practices. Educators should consider adopting interdisciplinary curricula that promote inquiry-based learning and real-world applications of scientific concepts. Professional development and collaborative planning should be prioritized to support teachers in implementing new instructional approaches effectively. Additionally, curriculum integration should be tailored to the needs of different grade levels and student groups, with additional support provided for those who struggle with transitions (Drake & Reid, 2018).

Future Actions

This study has prompted several areas for future research and action. Longitudinal studies are needed to examine the sustained impact of integrated curricula on teaching practices and student outcomes. Further research should also explore the specific challenges and successes of curriculum integration across different educational contexts and student

demographics. Additionally, investigating the impact of targeted professional development programs on teacher efficacy and student learning can provide valuable insights for educators and policymakers (Darling-Hammond, Hyler, & Gardner, 2017).

In conclusion, the integration of NGSS with IB PYP at CISB has shown promise in enhancing teaching practices and student outcomes. The findings underscore the potential benefits of interdisciplinary curricula and highlight the importance of targeted support for teachers and students. By continuing to explore and refine these approaches, educators can better prepare students for the challenges of the 21st century and promote a deeper understanding of scientific concepts and inquiry.

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